

Evaluation Methods for Deficits in Central Auditory Processing Among the Patients of Migraine**Mohd Khaja Moinuddin¹, Mohd Inamul Haq², Rabia Rafi³, Mohammad Naveed Ahamed⁴, Syed Iffat Yasmeen⁵, Naveen Kumar Korivipati⁶**¹Assistant Professor, Department of ENT, Shadan Institute of Medical Sciences, Hyderabad, Telangana²Assistant Professor, Department of ENT, Shadan Institute of Medical Sciences, Hyderabad, Telangana³Assistant Professor, Department of ENT, Shadan Institute of Medical Sciences, Hyderabad, Telangana⁴Professor and HOD, Department of ENT, Shadan Institute of Medical Sciences, Hyderabad, Telangana.⁵Assistant Professor, Department of ENT, Shadan Institute of Medical Sciences, Hyderabad, Telangana⁶Assistant Professor, Department of ENT, Shadan Institute of Medical Sciences, Hyderabad, Telangana

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Abstract:

Background: Migraine is a neurological disorder characterized by abnormal excitability in the visual, somatosensory, and motor cortices. Migraine may be a risk factor for developing HL and tinnitus. Investigating the relationship between Migraine and Hearing loss using different clinical tools and auditory instruments would encourage future research into the underlying patho-physiology and shared otologic principles between them. Hence comprehensive migraine prevention/treatment protocols may improve the outcomes of these associated otologic conditions. The present study was aimed to assess and compare auditory processing performance in migraine patients with and without dizziness, as well as in healthy controls.

Materials: 80 participants were divided into three groups: the control group (20 healthy subjects), study group I (30 subjects with migraine), and study group II (30 subjects with vestibular migraine). Participants were evaluated using the Central Auditory Processing Questionnaire for adults, tympanometry, pure tone audiometry, and psychophysical central auditory tests, Intelligibility in Noise Test, Gap in Noise Test.

Results: No significant differences were found between study groups I and II, but both study groups showed significant differences compared to the control group across all central auditory tests. A statistically significant difference was observed between the control group and both study groups in all memory tests. The highest percentage of abnormalities was noted in temporal resolution and selective auditory attention in both study groups. There was no significant correlation between the frequency of attacks per month and the central auditory test results.

Conclusions: Both migraine and vestibular migraine patients demonstrated poorer performance in all psychophysical central auditory tests compared to the control group. Additionally, there were no significant differences between the two study groups, suggesting that migraine, with or without dizziness, may share a similar underlying pathophysiology.

Keywords: Migraine, Central auditory processing, Memory, Attention, Auditory cortex.

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Introduction

Migraine is a prevalent and disabling primary headache disorder, often inherited and characterized by recurring, unilateral, throbbing headaches that worsen with movement and daily activities. [1] These attacks last ranging from 04 to 72 hours and are accompanied by nausea, vomiting, and heightened sensitivity to light and sound. [2] In migraine without aura (MoA), the headache is typically one-sided and pulsating, often linked with nausea and vomiting, lasting one to several days. [3] In contrast, migraine with aura (MA) is preceded by transient neurological symptoms like photophobia and phono-phobia. [4] Many migraine attacks originate

in the brain, with premonitory symptoms such as speech and reading difficulties, along with sensory hypersensitivity, which can often predict an impending attack. [5] Triggers such as stress, sleep disturbances, hunger, and excessive sensory stimulation further contribute to these episodes. [6] Clinical laboratory vestibular tests conducted on migraine patients, with or without dizziness, revealed a range of abnormalities, including both peripheral and central issues. [7] Additionally, some videonystagmographic abnormalities, such as positional nystagmus, canal paresis, and directional preponderance, were found in 55% of vestibular migraine

cases. [8] Central auditory processing (CAP) refers to how effectively and efficiently the central nervous system (CNS) processes auditory information. [9] Bellis et al. [10] defined central auditory processing disorders (CAPD) as deficiencies in one or more auditory functions, such as sound localization and lateralization, auditory discrimination, auditory pattern recognition, the temporal aspects of audition (resolution, masking, integration, ordering), auditory performance decrements in the presence of competing or degraded acoustic signals. [11] Previous research has reported abnormalities in the auditory brainstem response (ABR) in migraine patients, indicating potential auditory dysfunction and disruption of central auditory processing mechanisms. This malfunction could contribute to increased sound sensitivity in migraine sufferers, leading to phono-phobia. [12] The relationship between auditory dysfunction and migraine is still underexplored. While a few studies have investigated the connection between chronic migraine and auditory function, results remain limited and controversial. Agessi et al. [13] demonstrated that migraine may be linked to impairment in central auditory processing. Specifically, patients with migraine showed poor performance in tasks like auditory gap detection and distinguishing between short- and long-duration patterns, suggesting deficits in the physiological mechanisms of temporal processing, particularly in temporal resolution and ordering, compared to controls. [14] This study aims to explore the effects of migraine on various auditory processing abilities and compare the findings in vestibular migraine (VM) versus classic migraine.

Methods

This study was a case-control observational study conducted from June 2023 to May 2024 at Shadan Institute of Medical Sciences, Hyderabad, and Telangana.

Subjects of the Study: The study group included 80 adult patients: 30 subjects were with migraine and 30 were with vestibular migraine (VM), diagnosed according to the International Classification of Headache Disorders (ICHD-3, 2018), (15). Participants were aged between 18 and 60 years. An ethics committee approval was obtained before starting the study. An Ethics committee approved proforma and consent form were used for this study.

Inclusion Criteria: Study Group 1 (Migraine): Patients with at least five attacks of migraine meeting criteria B to D were included. Patients with Headache attacks lasting 04–72 hours (untreated or unsuccessfully treated) were included. Patients with Headaches have at least two of the following four characteristics: i. unilateral location. ii. Pulsating quality. iii. Moderate or severe intensity. iv. Aggravation by or avoidance of

routine physical activity (e.g., walking or climbing stairs). Patients having, during the headache, at least one of the following: i. Nausea and/or vomiting. ii. Photophobia and phono-phobia were included. All migraine patients were recruited from the headache and dizziness outpatient clinic at Shadan Institute of Medical Sciences.

Study Group 2 (Vestibular Migraine, VM): The criteria were: Patients with at least five episodes meeting criteria C and D were included. Patients with a history of migraine without aura or migraine with aura were included. Patients with Vestibular symptoms of moderate or severe intensity, lasting between 5 minutes and 72 hours were included. Patients with at least half of the episodes are associated with at least one of the following migraine features: i. Headache with at least two of the following characteristics: a. Unilateral location. b. Pulsating quality. c. Moderate or severe intensity. d. aggravation by routine physical activity. e. Photophobia and f. phono-phobia. g. Visual aura. Patients not better accounted for by another ICHD-3 diagnosis or by another vestibular disorder were included. Patients were examined between headache or vertigo episodes.

Exclusion Criteria: (for both study groups): Patients with other types of headache besides migraine were excluded. Patients with other neurological disorders were excluded.

Control-Group: The control group consisted of 20 healthy adults, matched for age with the study group. The inclusion criteria for the control group were as follows: 1. No history of migraine or other types of headache. 2. No history of neurological disorders. 3. No history of earache, ear discharge, or ear surgery.

Equipment-used: 1. A double-walled sound-treated room. 2. Two-channel audiometer, Interacoustics, model AC40 (Germany). 3. Acoustic immittance-meter, MAICO, model MI34 (USA). 4. GSI 61 clinical audiometer (USA).

Test Materials (Tools): 1. Gap in Noise Test (GIN), (14). 2. Duration Pattern Test (DPT), both verbal and humming versions (15).

Methods: The patients underwent the following assessments:

1. **Full neuro-otologic history**, which included:
 - A detailed history of migraine attacks, including demographic data (age, sex, educational level), any medical or psychiatric conditions, family history of migraine, and prior migraine treatments
 - A detailed personal history using the local language.
 - A detailed history of dizziness or vertigo, if present

- Associated auditory symptoms, such as tinnitus.
2. **Measurement of educational level:**
 - Low: if the subject was illiterate or had primary school education or could read and write
 - Middle: if the subject had preparatory or secondary school education
 - High: if the subject had a bachelor's, master's, PhD, or MD degree
 3. **Otological examination**
 4. **Basic audiological evaluation**, including pure-tone audiometry (air and bone conduction), speech audiometry, and Impedance audiometry.
 5. **Vestibular assessment:** Details were collected from patients' reports in the vestibular clinic
 6. **Psychophysical central auditory tests:** All tests were administered with subjects seated in a sound-treated room. Subjects received instructions and practice items prior to each test.

Statistical Analysis: Standard methods were used including: Mean, standard deviation (\pm SD), Minimum and maximum values (range) for numerical data and Frequency and percentage for non-numerical data.

Analytical-Statistics:

1. **One-way ANOVA:** To assess the statistical significance of differences between the means of more than two groups.

2. **Independent-samples t-test:** Used to assess the statistical significance of differences between the means of the two study groups.

3. **Pearson correlations:** Used to assess the strength and direction of the linear relationship between two quantitative variables (correlation coefficient, r).

4. **Chi-square test and Fisher's exact test:** Used to compare qualitative data between different groups. **P-value:** Level of significance: $P \leq 0.05$: Significant (S); $P \leq 0.01$: Highly significant (HS)

Results

The present study was conducted on 80 participants, divided into two main groups: a study group 1 (n = 30), study group 2 (n=30) and a control group (n = 20).

The study group 1 was called as Migraine group and the study group 2 was called as vestibular migraine group. The mean age for participants in study group 1 was 32.15 ± 4.8 years, while in study group 2, it was 33.5 ± 1.8 years. There were 19 (63.33%) females and 11 (36.66%) males in the group 1 and 20 (66.66%) females and 10 (%) males in the group 2.

In terms of gender distribution, both study group 1 and study group II showed a higher prevalence of migraine among females compared to males. Migraines were common in the participants with middle and high levels of education, followed by those with a low educational level (Table 1). The vestibular symptoms in vestibular migraine were highly variable. These symptoms included episodic true vertigo, positional vertigo, constant imbalance, movement-induced disequilibrium, and lightheadedness.

Table 1: Showing the demographic data and Migraine and Vertiginous Migraine features (n- Group 1- 30, Group 2- 30 and Control group- 20)

Observation	Group 1	Group 2	Control Group	P value
Age				
Mean	32.15	33.50	35.10	1.00
SD	4.8	1.8	2.65	
Range	24 to 48	22-44	28 to 49	
Gender				
Male	11	10	10	0.361
Female	19	20	10	
Education				
Low	06	03	10	0.01
Middle	14	15	05	
High	10	12	05	
Mean Duration of Migraine	1.2 \pm 0.25 Yrs	1.5 \pm 0.5 Yrs	--	0.01
Mean Number of Migraine Attacks	4 to 5	5 to 6	--	0.01
Vestibular symptoms				
episodic true vertigo	04	02		0.01
positional vertigo	06	06		
constant imbalance	03	07	--	
movement-induced disequilibrium	07	08		
lightheadedness	10	07		

An examination of headache characteristics in both groups revealed that most patients experienced unilateral and throbbing pain (Table 2), As a result, many patients reported significant impairment in their daily activities and work performance due to the severity of their migraines (Table 2).

The vestibular symptoms could occur before the headache, during the headache, or during a headache-free interval (Table 2). The most frequently reported auditory symptom in the present study was phono-phobia, with 95% of

patients in the migraine group and 85% in the vestibular migraine group reporting this symptom (Table 2).

When examined with positional tests it was observed that 25% of patients showed no VNG abnormalities. The most common finding was positional nystagmus, present in nearly 70% of patients, while caloric hypofunction was rare (5%). None of the patients exhibited oculomotor abnormalities (Table 2).

Table 2: Showing the Auditory, vestibular and ocular signs and symptoms in the Migraine participants (n- Group 1- 30, Group 2- 30 and Control group- 20)

Observation	Group 1- 30	Group 2- 30	Control Group- 20	P value
Side of Migraine				
Unilateral	24	02	--	0.144
Bilateral	06	08	--	
Nature of pain				
Throbbing	25	24	--	0.211
Wrenching	05	06	--	
Auditory symptoms				
Phono-phobia	26	27	--	0.301
No phono-phobia	04	03	--	
Vestibular signs and symptoms				
Positional nystagmus	20	21	--	0.410
Caloric hypofunction	10	09	--	
Ocular abnormalities	00	00	00	00

The most frequent complaints across both groups were related to memory and attention difficulties, followed by challenges with processing auditory information. The results of the central auditory processing tests, including the ability to understand speech in background noise, are presented in Table 3 for both the study and control groups. These results showed significantly lower scores in both study groups compared to the control group, with the mean scores falling below the 95% confidence limit of the control group, indicating abnormal central auditory processing.

A further comparison across the three groups revealed statistically significant differences in central auditory test results between both study groups and the control group. However, there was no significant difference between the migraine group and the vestibular migraine group. The SPIN (Speech in Noise) test showed the highest percentage of abnormal results in both study groups, with 100% of the vestibular migraine group (study group II) and 95% of the migraine group (study group I) showing impairments (Table 3). This abnormality was in line with the findings from the Auditory Processing Disorder (APD) questionnaire, where difficulty in understanding speech in background noise was a common complaint, reported by 65% of the migraine group and 75% of the vestibular migraine group (Table 3). Our results showed abnormal scores in both ears

with marked reduction in Lt Ear scores in both groups (Table 3). Furthermore, the mode of response to the duration pattern test was analyzed. It showed that the humming response was better than the verbal response in both groups (Table 3). As regards memory test results, migraine patients showed impaired memory function in all tests including recognition memory, memory for content, and memory for sequence tests. These results were consistent with the APD questionnaire as memory and attention were frequently encountered complaints in the APD questionnaire in both groups (Table 3). As such, it was evident that the migraine brain differs from the non-migraine brain. As shown in Table 03. All migraine patients in both groups had poor temporal resolution. While temporal patterning was affected in 85% group I and 95% group II.

The next affected ability was speech in noise discrimination and the least is dichotic listening. On the other hand, auditory memory abnormality was denoted in 55% in group I and 61% in group II denoting less affection of top-down cognitive processing than bottom-up processing. Regarding the vestibular migraine, there was no correlation between the number of attacks and the results of central auditory tests (Table 3), but there was a negative correlation between the duration of disease and some of the central auditory test results. All migraine patients in both groups had

poor temporal resolution. While temporal patterning was affected in 85% group I and 95% group II. The next affected ability was speech in noise discrimination and the least is dichotic listening. On the other hand, auditory memory abnormality was denoted in 55% in group I and 61% in group II denoting less affection of top-

down cognitive processing than bottom-up processing. Regarding the vestibular migraine, there was no correlation between the number of attacks and the results of central auditory tests (Tables 3), but there was a negative correlation between the duration of disease and some of the central auditory test results.

Table 3: Showing the central auditory processing test scores among the three groups of the study (n- Group 1- 30, Group 2- 30 and Control group- 20).

Observation	Group 1	Group 2	Control Group	P value
Central auditory processing test scores				
Ability to understand speech in background noise	06	07	20	0.001
SPIN (Speech in Noise)				
Left ear	25	26	Equal	0.001
Right Ear	05	04		
Memory test results				
Loss in Recognition memory	04	05	No loss	0.001
Loss in Memory for content	06	03		
Loss in Memory for sequence tests	05	07		
APD Questionnaire				
Memory related questions	15	18	Normal	0.001
Attention related questions	08	11		
Temporal patterning	22	24	Normal	0.001

Discussion

The present study was conducted on 80 participants, divided into two main groups: a study group 1 (n = 30), study group 2 (n=30) and a control group (n = 20). The study group 1 was called as Migraine group and the study group 2 was called as vestibular migraine group. The mean age for participants in study group 1 was 32.15±4.8 years, while in study group 2, it was 332.5±1.8 years. These findings were similar to the results of Burstein et al. [16], who reported a mean age of 32 years for migraine patients in their study. All participants in the study group had normal peripheral hearing, as shown in Table 1. There were 19 (%) females and 11 (%) males in the group 1 and 20 (%) females and 10 (%) males in the group 2. In terms of gender distribution, both study group 1 and study group II showed a higher prevalence of migraine among females compared to males. This finding was consistent with reports from Furman et al. [17] and Sohn[18].

The higher incidence of migraine in females is often attributed to hormonal fluctuations, particularly changes in estrogen levels, which are believed to trigger headaches in many women. In women headaches were reported just before or during menstruation, and others may experience migraines during pregnancy or menopause. [19, 20] It was observed in this study that migraines were common in the participants with middle and high levels of education, followed by those with a low educational level (Table 2). This observation was also reported by Hamed et al. [21], who found a higher

prevalence of migraines among individuals with middle educational levels and labor-intensive occupations. In addition, Lipton et al. [22] and Jeff [23] also reported higher migraine prevalence in lower social classes and among individuals with lower educational levels, likely due to the more physically demanding jobs, increased exposure to environmental stressors, and heightened life stress experienced by this group. Moreover, the study groups were matched for age, gender, and educational level (Table 1), ensuring balanced comparisons. There was no statistically significant difference between the two study groups in terms of disease duration or the number of migraine attacks (Table 2). In terms of family history, 50% of the patients in the migraine group reported a positive family history of migraine (Table 4), which aligns with the findings of Olsen and Russell [24], who estimated the heritability of migraine to be between 40% and 60%. In contrast, only 20% of the vestibular migraine group reported a positive family history, which is consistent with Hazza et al [25], who found a family history in just 16% of vestibular migraine patients. An examination of headache characteristics in both groups revealed that most patients experienced unilateral and throbbing pain (Table 3), a result consistent with Loder et al. [26], who reported that approximately two-thirds of their migraine patients experienced unilateral and throbbing headaches. Most participants in the current study also identified several common triggers for their migraine attacks, including lack of sleep, stress, travel, fasting, and exposure to certain odors. As a result, many patients reported significant im-

pairment in their daily activities and work performance due to the severity of their migraines (Table 4). This is in agreement with Hamed et al. [21], who reported that 65% of migraine patients in Upper Egypt had severe attacks that halted their daily routines. The most frequently reported auditory symptom in the present study was phonophobia, with 95% of patients in the migraine group and 85% in the vestibular migraine group reporting this symptom (Table 4). This finding is consistent with the study by Alborzi et al. [27], who also identified phonophobia as the most common auditory symptom in migraine patients. The most common auditory symptom in this study was phonophobia, which frequently occurred in association with photophobia. In our findings, the same proportion of patients who experienced phonophobia in both the migraine and vestibular migraine groups also reported photophobia (Table 4). This is consistent with the work of Vingen et al. (28), who found that the same number of patients who complained of phonophobia also experienced photophobia. The vestibular symptoms in vestibular migraine were highly variable. These symptoms included episodic true vertigo, positional vertigo, constant imbalance, movement-induced disequilibrium, and lightheadedness (Fig. 2). The vestibular symptoms could occur before the headache, during the headache, or during a headache-free interval (Figs. 3 and 4). Neuhauser et al. [29] reported that all forms of dizziness could occur in patients with migraine. When examined with positional tests it was observed that 25% of patients showed no VNG abnormalities. The most common finding was positional nystagmus, present in nearly 70% of patients, while caloric hypofunction was rare (5%). None of the patients exhibited oculomotor abnormalities (Table 5). These results align with Hazzaa et al. [25], who studied VNG in 98 patients with vestibular migraine and found positional nystagmus in nearly 60% of subjects. The present study showed that the findings support the hypothesis that vestibular migraine is associated with peripheral vestibular lesions. Furman [17] also proposed that migraine may induce vasospasm, leading to a decrease in regional blood flow to the inner ear via the internal auditory artery, which branches from the anterior inferior cerebellar artery (AICA). This could result in transient ischemia and potentially cause temporary or permanent peripheral vestibular dysfunction. Multiple studies have documented that migraine can lead to both permanent auditory and vestibular deficits due to repeated circulation issues and plasma extravasation during migraine attacks. As a result, patients with chronic, repeated migraine attacks may be more susceptible to peripheral vestibular dysfunction. Table 6 and Figure 4 display the results from the Central Auditory Processing Questionnaire. The most frequent complaints across both groups were related to memory

and attention difficulties, followed by challenges with processing auditory information. The results of the central auditory processing tests, including the ability to understand speech in background noise, are presented in Tables 7 and 8 for both the study and control groups. These results showed significantly lower scores in both study groups compared to the control group, with the mean scores falling below the 95% confidence limit of the control group, indicating abnormal central auditory processing. A further comparison across the three groups revealed statistically significant differences in central auditory test results between both study groups and the control group. However, there was no significant difference between the migraine group and the vestibular migraine group. These findings are consistent with Dash et al. [30], who reported that there were no significant differences in clinical symptoms or cochleovestibular findings between migraine patients with or without vertigo. The SPIN (Speech in Noise) test showed the highest percentage of abnormal results in both study groups, with 100% of the vestibular migraine group (study group II) and 95% of the migraine group (study group I) showing impairments (Table 9). This abnormality was in line with the findings from the Auditory Processing Disorder (APD) questionnaire, where difficulty in understanding speech in background noise was a common complaint, reported by 65% of the migraine group and 75% of the vestibular migraine group (Table 9 and Fig. 4). This suggests that migraine patients experience severe impairments in speech discrimination in noisy environments, with no significant difference between the two study groups. These results support the findings of Hosein et al. [31], who reported that migraine patients without aura have difficulty perceiving speech in background noise and experience a loss in signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) during the Quick Speech in Noise (Q-SIN) test. This showed an abnormal increase compared to the control group. This was attributed to the structural and functional changes including the presence of white matter lesions under the cortex and thickening of the cortical regions that have been confirmed by imaging studies in people with migraine. Krishnamurti [32] proved that the SPIN test is a useful procedure with moderate sensitivity to a variety of central auditory nervous system [CANS] disorder at different levels in the brain. Accordingly, SPIN test results should be interpreted cautiously in association with other central auditory tests as it is non-localizing to the site of lesion. Regarding the dichotic integration ability, the DDT was used. Our results showed abnormal scores in both ears with marked reduction in Lt ear scores in both groups (Table 7). This denoted affection of higher auditory pathways mostly at the cortical level. This agreed with Morlet et al. [33], who found that problems in dichotic integration during the nonverbal dichotic test [NVDT] and

abnormal N1 peak related to attention in the long latency response test were observed in people with migraine. The Gap in Noise [GIN] Test in this study was used to evaluate the auditory temporal resolution ability at the cortical level of the brain. The results showed the highest percent of abnormality, 100% in both groups (Table 7). These results were consistent with the study conducted by Agessi et al. [13] who observed that adults with migraine presented with impairment in the physiologic mechanism of temporal processing, especially in temporal resolution and temporal ordering when compared with controls. The difference in performance on the GIN Test between patients with migraine and the control group may denote a central auditory system dysfunction in migraine patients either with or without dizziness. The DPT test results showed reduced scores in the two migraine groups when compared with control (Table 7 and Fig. 5). Furthermore, the mode of response to the duration pattern test was analyzed. It showed that the humming response was better than the verbal response in both groups (Table 10). This means that the response was hummed more correctly, denoting normal function of the right hemisphere. On the other hand, patients had difficulty reporting the response verbally denoting dysfunction either in the left hemisphere or interhemispheric pathways. There was no difference in performance between the two groups of migraine. As regards memory test results, migraine patients showed impaired memory function in all tests including recognition memory, memory for content, and memory for sequence tests. This was consistent with Zeitlin and Oddy[34] who found that in a group of patients with severe migraine, they had significantly poorer performances in memory and information processing tests. These results were consistent with the APD questionnaire as memory and attention were frequently encountered complaints in the APD questionnaire in both groups (Table 6 and Fig. 4). Similarly, a systematic review by Barbosa et al. [35] studied 23 articles to evaluate cognitive impairment in migraine. They found that patients with migraine especially those followed at neurology clinics, often report cognitive complaints, especially regarding attention and memory. The most important cognitive functions include attention, short-term memory, and working memory. These cognitive activities act as compensatory mechanisms of the auditory system in cases of affected bottom-up processing such as lack of temporal encoding. From all the previous results, we can hypothesize that migraine is triggered by a bottom-up mechanism from the brain stem up to the higher cortex. This agreed with Borsook and Burstein [36]. They suggested that migraine was more than a headache. It was viewed as a complex neurological disorder that affects multiple cortical, subcortical, and brainstem areas which regulate autonomic, affective,

cognitive, and sensory functions. As such, it was evident that the migraine brain differs from the non-migraine brain. As shown in Table 11, temporal processing was the most frequently affected central auditory ability. All migraine patients in both groups had poor temporal resolution. While temporal patterning was affected in 85% group I and 95% group II. The next affected ability was speech in noise discrimination and the least is dichotic listening. On the other hand, auditory memory abnormality was denoted in 55% in group I and 61% in group II denoting less affection of top-down cognitive processing than bottom-up processing. The correlation studies that compared the duration of migraine, the frequency of attack, and the central auditory test results in study group I showed that there was no correlation (Tables 12 and 13). Similarly, Hosein et al. [31] found that migraine patients without aura have difficulty in speech perception in background noise, but there was no correlation between the duration of the disease or the frequency of attacks and [SNR] loss. Regarding the vestibular migraine, there was no correlation between the number of attacks and the results of central auditory tests (Tables 12 and 13), but there was a negative correlation between the duration of disease and some of the central auditory test results. This may be related to the long presence of vestibular symptoms not to migraine duration itself. This agreed with Neuhauser et al. [29]. In addition, there was no difference in performance between vestibular and non-vestibular migraine. This may indicate that subclinical vestibular dysfunction is an integral part of migraine pathology in general and not only in vestibular migraine. Accordingly, it can be assumed that the large overlap between migraine pathways and vestibular pathways and this is consistent with the view that vestibular migraine is a migraine variant with vestibular manifestations. Finally, the present study showed that most patients with migraine-type headaches may experience changes. Individuals with migraines may experience changes in their auditory processing abilities at various stages of an attack, potentially impacting their ability to perform tasks at work or at home. This decline in central auditory processing, if not addressed early, can negatively affect their quality of life. We recommend conducting a follow-up longitudinal study to explore how different medical treatments influence the central auditory processing in these patients. We anticipate improvements in central auditory test scores, particularly in cognitive functions.

Limitations of the study

The patients in this study were receiving various forms of migraine treatment and experienced different levels of migraine severity. However, this variability did not affect the results, as the majority of participants exhibited abnormal test scores, with

the results showing a correlation to the frequency and duration of attacks.

Conclusions

Patients with both migraine and vestibular migraine demonstrated poorer performance across all psychophysical central auditory tests compared to the control group. Moreover, no significant differences were found between the two study groups in terms of central auditory test results, suggesting that migraines with and without dizziness may share similar underlying pathophysiology.

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